

Improving Deep Neural Net Aerial Lidar Point Cloud Object Classification Accuracy using a Second Processing Pass

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Summary

Automated classification of objects in point clouds (e.g. sourced from LiDAR) has received an increase in attention in recent years. This research explores how a second classification pass can be used to improve the initial classification results by using the class labels from the spatial neighbourhood. In this pursuit, we build on an existing voxel-based MPVCNN architecture to explore the potential of such an approach in improving classification accuracy (F1-score). The model was trained and tested on the Vaihingen 3D LiDAR dataset, and resulted in an improvement to the F1-score for specific objects like cars. Future work will explore the use of this method in other non-voxel based deep learning architectures such as PointNet++.

KEYWORDS:

deep learning, aerial LiDAR, classification, segmentation

1. Introduction

The majority of recent research in point cloud semantic segmentation tasks has focused on the development of deep learning architectures. In this paper, our approach is to improve the predicted class label generated from existing deep learning architectures, by using that class label as an input to a subsequent processing pass. In other words, to check the classification outputs within their neighbourhood and correct the class on a second pass. To obtain a predicted class for each individual point, the coordinate data needs to be first processed by a deep learning model. Subsequently, this predicted class information is used to preprocess the input data into another run through the deep learning model (or a different architecture).

Aerial point cloud data generated from LiDAR scans pose unique challenges in the form of varying point density, a large variation in outdoor object physical sizes and accounting for different surface properties. Therefore, in point cloud segmentation tasks, it is common to supplement coordinate data from LiDAR scans with calculated geometric properties as additional input features. Geometric features (e.g. eigenvalue, planarity, verticality, roughness) can be derived from eigenvalue decomposition of given point coordinates. This approach is found to be adopted across various aerial point cloud deep learning architectures including feature image (NANJ2 2018 [9], TONIC 2021 [5]), voxel (MPVCNN 2022 [6]), direct point cloud (GADH-Net 2020 [2], Modified Pointnet++ 2021 [1]) and transformers (MPT+ 2022 [8]).

Either a fixed radius or k-nearest neighbours are used to define a neighbourhood, and geometric properties are calculated from points that reside within that neighbourhood area, and it is likely that the

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points within that area will consist of several object classes (e.g. cars, trees, roads will be near each other). Therefore, the engineered geometric features (e.g. verticality) may be calculated from a mixed group of neighbouring points, for instance a road and a nearby car. A better representation would be to calculate verticality from cars separately to that of roads, however this filtering is not possible on the raw unclassified LiDAR point cloud.

This research explores the use of class labels as a point filtering criterion for the calculation of geometric properties, and also class labels as a direct input to deep learning architecture, with an aim of achieving higher accuracy in point cloud segmentation. The former option is to use the predicted class labels (i.e. after a first classification run) as a criterion to select nearby points with the same class label as the index point. Geometric features can be calculated based on a group of points of similar class. A second option is to use class label of individual points to determine the surrounding neighbourhood point. For example, for an index point representing 'car', it is likely to be surrounded by neighbourhood points of 'car' or 'road'. This neighbourhood information could be added as input data, in addition to its coordinate and geometric features.

2. Related Work

To the best of our knowledge, no other study has explored the approach of introducing a second pass to take the predicted class labels as an input to a further segmentation task in a data processing pipeline. To generate first pass class labels, an existing deep learning architecture MPVCNN [6] was used in this study. MPVCNN is suited for aerial point cloud datasets, with advantages in terms of low training time and low computational demand [6].

To demonstrate the benefit of filtering by geometric features, minimal changes are made to the MPVCNN design. In this voxel-based architecture, the points are sampled and encoded through a voxelization step. As such, geometric features are calculated and classes filtered as a pre-processing step, prior to the voxelization step, as described in section 3.2.

To explore the effect of class labels as input data, changes are performed on the MPVCNN design to capture the class label as an input. This is further described in section 3.3

3. Methodology

3.1 Dataset

The International Society for Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing (ISPRS) 3D Vaihingen semantic labeling dataset by Niemeyer et, al [4] was used for this research (see Figure 1). It is an airborne laser scanned dataset acquired using a Leica ALS50 system over Vaihingen city in Germany, with a sparse point density of 6.7 points per m². The lidar data are categorized into nine semantic classes which are powerline, low vegetation, impervious surface, fence hedge, car, roof, facade, shrub, and tree. Three different areas are provided: one area with 753,876 points as the training set and other two areas with 411,722 points as the testing sets. In this work, xyz coordinate and intensity ("xyzi") values are used. For batch training, we adopted the same approach used by GADH-Net [2], the training data was divided into 25m x 25m blocks with overlap of 12.5m - to eliminate edge effects and increase the number of data points used for training.

Figure 1: Vaihingen City (Germany) LiDAR dataset [4] (a) train data in 9 object classes (b) train data perspective view (c) test data in 9 object classes

3.2 Filtered geometric features into MPVCNN

Data consisting of 3D coordinates (xyz), LiDAR intensity return value and geometric features consists of eigenentropy (“E”), planarity (“P”), verticality (“V”), roughness (“R”), local point density (“D”) were processed through MPVCNN-base the first time to generate individual point predicted class label. In this first pass, geometric features are calculated using fixed number of neighbours (either $k=5$ or $k=10$) around each index point. For the second pass, leveraging from the result of the predicted class label, geometric features are re-calculated only from nearby points that share the same class label as the index points, with fixed nearest neighbour search ($k=5$ or $k=10$). In other words, ‘tree’ planarity is calculated from point belonging to the ‘tree’ class as predicted in the 1st pass (“MPVCNN-base”), and so on for each class in turn.

There is also another consideration on the training and testing data when applying class filter for geometric features in the second pass MPVCNN. The training data in its original form is ‘clean’ in the

way that all points are correctly class labelled. On the other hand, the testing data when processed by MPVCNN-base generates predicted labels with around 80% accuracy. Therefore, there is a possibility of the second pass model will be trained on geometric features calculated from all correctly labelled points, but tested on geometric features calculated from 80% accurately labelled points. To mitigate this effect, a ‘noisy’ training data was generated by predicting class labels on the training data using MPVCNN-base. This generated about 80% accurately predicted class labels for the training dataset, which was used to filter points in geometric features calculation, thus making the second pass MPVCNN model to learn from a ‘noisy’ dataset. The effect of this is further explained in section 4.

Preference is given to geometric features with distinctive distribution according to class label. For example, low value of verticality for ‘façade’ (class label 6 in Figure 2a) demarcates itself from other object classes. Whereas plant-like objects such as ‘shrub’ (class label 7) and ‘tree’ (class label 8) have wider spread of roughness values as depicted in Figure 2b. It can also be observed from the same Figure 2(a) and 2(b) that objects like ‘car’ (class label 3) and ‘fence hedge’ (class label 4) share very similar features, thus adding to the complexity of classifying point clouds from these two objects.

Figure 2(a): Geometric feature verticality $k=10$ (class filtered)

Figure 2(b): Geometric feature roughness $k=10$ (class filtered)

3.3 Filtered class data as neighbourhood information into MPVCNN

Classifying points class labels using a prior predicted class as a direct input may lead to model overfitting. To reduce this effect, we added another feature which represents the neighbourhood point class information. This neighbourhood information is defined as the other class label(s) which is dissimilar to the index point. The neighbourhood points are determined by radius neighbour search in the range of $1 < r < 3$, to prevent from choosing the index points class label itself and other points too near to the index point which may be predicted with the wrong class label from the 1st pass MPVCNN. Up to two most common classes are then stored.

There are several design options to fuse this neighbourhood information with the geometric & coordinate information into MPVCNN. In this paper, we only consider early fusion at the input data level. Other fusion options namely intermediate fusion of feature maps and late fusion at classification level are to be included in the future.

Since the neighbourhood information is a categorical data, this feature is first encoded as numerical values via an embedding step. The output is then combined with other input features such as coordinates and geometric features before processed by MPVCNN as a second pass.

4. Experiment & Results

Results of this experiment are presented in the form of F1-scores per class (Table 1) and confusion matrix per point (Figure 3). The experiments were done on two sets of geometric features, namely 'EPVD' with $k=5$ and 'PVRD' with $k=10$. As baseline, prediction result of MPVCNN is included in Table 1 as Experiment A1.

The effect of class filtered geometric features when trained on 'noisy' data can be observed from Experiments A1-D1 in Figure 3(a) and 3(d). With a second pass MPVCNN and 'noisy' training data, there is a noticeable benefit in reducing false positives for 'car' objects previously predicted as 'low veg' and 'shrub', as depicted by 'red' boxes in Figure 3(a) and 3(b). Nonetheless, there are also instances of increased false negatives whereby points belonging to 'low veg' are predicted as 'car' - indicated by 'green' boxes in the same figures. This can be observed in Figures 4(a), 4(b) and 4(c), where the 'purple' boxes indicate points where 'shrub' being wrongly predicted as 'car' in Experiment A1 and lesser in D1. Overall, there is a net F1-score gain for targeted object such as 'car', which is a desirable effect.

In terms of the use of class filtered geometric features on 'clean' training data, the result has shown a mixed trend between Experiments A1-B1 and Experiments A2-B2. In Experiments A1-B1, geometric feature set of 'EPVD' $k=5$ has no appreciable gain from the use of class filters or neighbourhood information. Whereas with geometric feature set of 'PVRD' $k=10$ in Experiments A2-B2, class filters regained F1-score for objects such as 'car' and 'shrub'.

The use of neighbourhood information in the form of early input data fusion has no gain in terms of F1-score, as can be observed from Experiments A1-C1 and Experiments A2-C2 in Table 1.

Table 1: F1-scores

Nr	Experiment	Input data	Power Line (0)	Low vegetation (1)	Imperious surface (2)	Car (3)	Fence hedge (4)	Roof (5)	Façade (6)	Shrub (7)	Tree (8)	OA
A1	MPVCNN-base (no filter geom features)	XYZI EPV (k=5, D (r=3)	0.664	0.801	0.900	0.643	0.402	0.915	0.583	0.436	0.766	0.811
B1	MPVCNN 2 nd pass (class filtered geom features)	XYZI EPV (k=5, D (r=3)	0.499	0.782	0.883	0.631	0.349	0.899	0.531	0.419	0.761	0.793
C1	MPVCNN 2 nd pass (neighbour class & no filter geom features)	XYZI EPV (k=5, D (r=3) neighbour class $1 < r < 3$	0.499	0.793	0.893	0.558	0.353	0.903	0.546	0.407	0.766	0.801
D1	MPVCNN 2 nd pass (class filtered geom features), train data with noise	XYZI EPV (k=5, D (r=3)	0.563	0.788	0.891	0.674	0.314	0.908	0.566	0.425	0.763	0.801
A2	MPVCNN-base (no filter geom features)	XYZI PVR (k=10, D (r=3)	0.625	0.800	0.900	0.601	0.357	0.927	0.588	0.406	0.785	0.817
B2	MPVCNN 2 nd pass (class filtered geom features)	XYZI PVR (k=10, D (r=3)	0.607	0.769	0.893	0.635	0.351	0.922	0.585	0.427	0.780	0.809
C2	MPVCNN 2 nd pass (neighbour class & class filtered geom features)	XYZI PVR (k=10, D (r=3) neighbour class $1 < r < 3$	0.553	0.803	0.902	0.564	0.311	0.912	0.586	0.406	0.786	0.813

(a) A1 - MPVCNN-base

(b) D1 – MPVCNN 2nd pass with class filter geometric features k=5, trained on ‘noisy’ data

(c) A2 – MPVCNN 2nd pass with no class filter geometric features k=10

(d) B2 - MPVCNN 2nd pass with class filtered geometric features k =10 & neighbourhood information

Figure 3: Confusion matrix

Figure 4(a) Test data ground truth ('car')

Figure 4(b) Test data predicted A1 MPVCNN-base ('car')

Figure 4(c) Test data predicted D1 MPVCNN 2nd pass ('car')

5. Conclusion

This research has demonstrated that class-based filtering before calculation of selected geometric features increases F1-scores on certain object, such as ‘car’ in the Vaihingen dataset. This could be useful in use cases to detect specific objects such as ‘car’ and higher accuracy is needed. Nonetheless, when this technique is implemented in MPVCNN, its voxelization step may gather points and geometric features from different objects that resides within the same voxel, despite been previously class filtered. Therefore, voxel-based architectures may limit the effectiveness of class filtered method. Unlike in direct point cloud deep learning architecture such as Pointnet++[7], whereby the selection of neighbouring points and features around a centroid point is expected to enable an effective class filtering.

Further work shall explore the effect class filtered geometric features and class information on other non voxel-based deep learning architectures, and other fusion methodologies.

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